

ヨーロッパの木製バイオマスエネルギーコジェネレーションのトレンド

European trends in wood biomass energy cogeneration

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Then God said, ‘Let the land produce vegetation: seed-bearing plants and trees on the land ...’ And it was so. The land produced vegetation: plants bearing seed according to their kinds and trees ... And God saw that it was good. And there was evening, and there was morning – the third day. [Genesis 1:11-13]

Abstract:

In this article we report on scalable modern commercial wood gas cogeneration technology of micro scale, beginning at 9 kW electric power, scalable up to 1 MW electric power, as offered by several European companies. Cogeneration means to use both electricity and heat, which leads to an overall efficiency of converting the chemical energy in wood up to 80% or 90%.

本稿において、私は、9kW 電力（マイクロスケール）から、いくつかのヨーロッパの会社が提供する最高1MW 電力まで、さまざまなスケールの現代商業用木製ガスコジェネレーションテクノロジーを報告する。コジェネレーション（熱電併給）は、電気および熱を利用することによって、木材の化学エネルギーの変換効率を最高80%または90%にまで高めることができる。

I. Introduction

The development which we address here is about the technology of using wood biomass in the form of wood chips (or wood pellets) for sustainable renewable energy production. This means both electricity generation and production of useful heat for heating, for (adsorption) cooling, for drying, and for warm water for living. We do not report on the latest research laboratory level technology, but on technology that is on the market, well tested, fully competitive and commercial, i.e. off the shelf technology, free of technological adventures.

For this research, we have spoken with a wide range of domestic and international experts from the industry, government, administration, and public research laboratories, and we have visited a range of commercial profit-making projects in several countries where wood gas cogeneration technology is in long term routine daily use, since several years [Project Activities 2015]. Beyond 200kW electric power (200kWel) per unit, there are *updraft* fixed bed and for even higher power *fluidized-bed* gasifiers [VTT 2015, DBFZ Report 18, Syncraft 2017], which we do not discuss here.

As we will see in this report, modern commercial European (downdraft) wood gas combined heat and power (CHP) units (cogenerators) already provide on and off grid electric power from 9kWel to 1MWel plus twice that in terms of thermal power. Annual operating hours range up to 8500h with inexpensive local wood chip fuel. Demand for this genuine 21st century technology increases worldwide.

An incentive for universities may be the obvious educational benefits by involving students in planning, design, set up, operation, maintenance and monitoring. Yoensu University of Finland [Yoensu 2015], and Technical University of Dresden/Hochschule Zittau in Germany [Zittau 2009] have decided to actively research and apply wood gas cogeneration.

Section II reports on wood gas cogeneration projects in southern Germany. It includes a brief paragraph on the general principle of wood gas cogeneration, and information on German market

development. Section III describes wood gas cogeneration in Lower Austria and Section IV in Finland. Finally Section V discusses technological, economic and political sustainability of wood gas cogeneration. This is followed by a conclusion.

II. Wood gas cogeneration projects in Southern Germany

The first encounter was with an Urbas wood gas cogenerator on the scenic German tourist island of Mainau in the Lake of Constance. The machine is manufactured by an Austrian company Urbas Energy Technology. In this project wood from local forests is chipped on site (with a leased wood chipper, providing chips for several months in several hours) and continuously fed (Fig. 1) into the *wood gas cogenerator* (Fig. 2) producing heat for gastronomy (tourist restaurant facilities (Fig. 3), wedding receptions), and show green houses, open for up to 6000 daily visitors. The electricity produced is sold to the public utility company of the nearby City of Konstanz. A speciality of this model are that for detarification ceramic candles have to be periodically exchanged and cleaned before reuse. And the wood chips have to be relatively massive. [Urbas 2015], [Mainau 2015].

Generally, dry wood chips enter through a double door (to remove air) into an over 1000 °C hot pyrolysis chamber from above. Automatic process control ensures that the wood molecules are thermally cracked completely (no tar remains) into gas molecules, with a fine ash content of 1-2%. The fine dry pure carbon ash is automatically removed by textile filters, dropping into the ash removal pipe. The clean pure gas is cooled down with water for combustion in an off-the-shelf high quality, long life diesel (non turbo) engine, attached to an electric generator, rated between 9 kWel and 56 kWel. The removed heat corresponds to approximately twice the electric power.

Fig. 1. Wood chips on Mainau Island.

Fig. 2 and part of Urbas wood gas cogenerator on German tourist island of Mainau in the Lake of Constance, Summer 2014.

Fig. 3. Mainau Island Restaurants space heating/warm water by Wood Gas Cogeneration.

Next, was the first wood gas cogenerators, manufactured by the Lower Bavarian (German:

Niederbayern) Company Spanner Re², on a cooperative farm in Herdwangen, in the southern Black Forest region. The farmers faithfully and enthusiastically operated this machine for over seven years and continue to experiment with inserting a variety of forest residues, even including loads of pine needles. The wood gas cogenerator has an overall efficiency of up to 90% of turning the wood's chemical energy into electricity (approx. 1/3) and heat (approx. 2/3). [Heggelbach 2015] [Spanner Re 2015] [Ecolifelab 2014]

Furthermore, we went to Giglberg/Velden in Lower Bavaria itself and toured two less than one year old state-of-the-art modern Spanner Re² wood gas cogenerators (Fig. 4 right, Fig 5) in continuous automatic operation of up to 7800 hours per year [Josef Strobl 2015]. Electricity (Fig. 5 right) and heat are used by local residents, who are connected to a small local district heating network. Wood chips (Fig. 4 left) are delivered periodically by truck, and the gas engines are maintained periodically, exactly like engines of commercial vehicles. The expected life time of these wood gas cogenerators is over 20 years.

Fig. 4. Spanner Re² wood gas cogenerator installed by Josef Strobl Heizung Solar in Giglberg and Velden/Vils/Lower Bavaria/Germany. Left: suitable dry wood chips. Right: modern 100% wood to gas pyrolysis unit.

Fig. 5. Spanner Re² wood gas cogenerator installed by Josef Strobl Heizung Solar in Giglberg and Velden/Vils/Lower Bavaria/Germany. Left: pyrolysis unit in left image half. Gas engine and generator on right half. Right: enlarged image of gas engine and generator.

In Germany, wood gas cogenerator technology has since 2011 become market dominant over steam turbines and ORC turbines (see Fig. 6). Note that decreasing feed-in tariffs in Germany levelled off the national growth of wood gas CHPs since 2014, but the target of mature commercial technology has been achieved [Spanner KK Japan brochure 2017].

Power generation from woody biomass in Germany

Fig 6. Development of solid biomass power plant technologies. Pink bars and trend curve for gas engines, i.e. predominantly wood gasification [Lenz 2017].

It is important to provide wood chips of *sufficient dryness* (less than 13% fuel moisture, Fig. 4 left) for the effortless smooth operation of a wood gas cogenerator. Wood chips can be from chipped, sieved and dried forest wood or road side vegetation, or from transport palettes and crates [Spanner KK 2017]. If the water content of the available wood chip fuel should be too high, some of the cogenerated heat from the cogenerator itself can optionally be used to complete the drying process. Makers already offer a wide range of products with such additional functionality as optional add ons, including drying conveyors, silo dryers, push floor dryers, drying containers, double bin dryers and combi dryers [Spanner Dryers 2015], [Sanyo 2015]. Companies like Spanner KK in Japan, decided to always include a fuel drying unit.

A modern Spanner Re² 45 kW electric, 105 kW heat wood gas cogenerator can normally supply 70 families with electricity and heat from storable, renewable and sustainable wood chip fuel. In the case of emergency up to 7000 families can be provided with high priority electricity for night time lighting and telecommunication [Safe City Japan Project 2014]. The world market leader Spanner Re² operates wood gas CHPs since 2008, has already shipped over 700 units to 14 countries, installed 30MWel and 66MW of thermal power (MWth), average operating hours per year are 7500h per unit, and clocked up over 20 Mio. operating hours in total. For on and off grid operation and diesel generator replacement Spanner Re² offers scalable EnergyBlock container modules. Typical customers are municipalities, schools, community housing, district heat suppliers, hotels, sawmills, farms, and power stations [Spanner KK 2017]. The new small sized 9kWel, 22kWth Spanner HKA10 model can operate with three types of fuel: wood chips, wood pellets and wood brickets. It is housed in a single 2.10 x 1.40 x 2.20 m³ (L x W x H) casing, and quick to install with plug-and-play connections [Spanner Re 2017].

III. Wood gas cogenerators in Lower Austria

In March 2017, I had the opportunity to visit the factory of Froeling GesmbH in Grieskirchen, Lower Austria. They are specialists for biomass heating for individual houses up to district heating network MWel scale thermal supply. All parts are designed inhouse by Froeling and manufactured locally with 10 years of guarantee even on wear and tear parts. Even after 25 years customers can call the company and request spare parts, which are either in storage, or will simply be remanufactured according to the original specifications. Traditionally the company also offers complete systems with fuel intake mechanisms, heaters (boilers) and hot water storage, control systems (Fig. 8), indoor and outdoor (container) systems, they offer combination heaters that work

with split wood or pellets, and wood gasification heaters. Recently they decided to enter the high end wood gas cogenerator (Fig. 7, centre) market with electric power models of 46-56kWel (95-115kWth), and a high end commercial gas engine (Fig. 7, right), offering both indoor and container outdoor models (Fig. 7, left), fuelled with wood chips. The turn-key ready wood gas cogenerators are completely assembled and tested in operation at the factory, before being shipped worldwide. Like other brands, customers frequently scale up the power by operating several wood gas CHP units in parallel. Options include sliding floor drying (primarily with waste heat) and size filtering, where rejected fuel can still be used in wood chip boilers [Froeling CHP 2017].

Fig. 7. Left: Froeling outdoor model container in testing with pyrolysis unit, gas engine and generator inside. Center: pyrolysis unit in container (fuel inlet double lock in top right). Right: gas engine and generator prepared by company engineers for testing.

Fig. 8. Left: Control panel for fuel intake, pyrolysis unit, ash removal, gas cooling, and heat exchange with temperature and pressure sensor values. Right: Control panel for gas engine, engine cooling, engine oil pressure and temperature, electric generator (temperature, voltage, current, power).

IV. Advanced wood gas cogeneration in Finland

We also used an opportunity to visit the Gasification Technology Department of the National Finish VTT Laboratories in Espoo, near Helsinki, Finland [VTT 2015]. VTT's Mr. Illka Hiltunen, the experienced group leader of a group of 15 researchers guided us. He showed advanced industrial research laboratory setups, and explained various large-scale industrial biomass gasification projects that have been developed at VTT and are now in commercial operation since a number of years. The northern Finish company Volter Oy [Volter Oy 2015] from Kempele, near Oulu, contacted VTT in order to measure and certify the performance of Volter Oy wood gas cogenerators in downdraft technology. VTT researchers were utterly surprised by the high quality and reliability of the Volter Oy devices, developed independently in the industrial laboratory of the small Volter Oy company founded in 1998 by Juha Sipilae, who is now Finland's new prime minister.

We subsequently paid a visit to the Volter Oy company itself in Kempele. The manager Jarno Haapakoski showed us the company's own device in operation, powering a local grid-independent bioenergy village of some 13 houses, and showed us a range of residential projects (Fig. 9) powered by Volter Oy wood gas cogenerators in the region, in operation since a variety of years. Volter Oy devices seem to be among the state-of-the-art world wide.

The process is highly efficient, and at the same time simplified. All components are made of stainless steel, to guarantee longevity of use. The utterly compact 4.5 ton machine itself with dimensions of 4.8 x 1.3 x 2.5 m³ fits comfortably into a container or on a truck. Dry wood chip fuel consumption in full power operation is 4.5 m³/24h (900 kg/24h). It has 40kW electrical, 100kW heat and 20kW hot air output, and the electric output can be adjusted in operation between 30-100% within 60 seconds. Moreover, for easy and fast startup the machine can be kept in standby mode for up to seven days. The device is so reliable and flexible in use, that Volter Oy recently even received an order from the Finish Yoensu University for a truck mounted wood gas cogenerator in order to provide energy for sports events, conferences and concerts, etc. [Volter Oy 2015] Wood gas cogenerators *Volter 40* are now also imported to Japan by Volter Japan [Volter KK 2017].

Fig. 9. Volter Oy wood gas cogenerator facilities near Kempele/Oulu/Finland. Left: hydraulic roof wood chip fuel storage. Centre: warm water buffer tank. Right: compact wood gas cogenerator. Supplying 32 residential units (see above layout drawing) with total floor space of 2365 m² [Liikkujantie 19 2015].

The fuel supply can also be designed very practical and compact. One example is like a personal garage with a hydraulic roof (Fig. 9, left), opened remotely, a wood chip truck moves in front of it, dumps its load of wood chips, and the roof is closed again remotely, thus providing supply for several weeks.

V. The sustainability of wood gas cogenerators

V.1 Technological sustainability

Historically, wood gasification was invented as long ago as 1839 by Karl Gustav Bischof, professor of chemistry at Bonn University in Germany [Krenkel 1955]. A wood gas generator for mobile use was invented in 1921 by the French-German engineer Georges Imbert [Hagen 2015]. At the end of

the 1930ies ca. 9000 wood gas powered vehicles were in use [Decker 2015] and during WWII approx. six million [Hagen 2015].

Like for a car, a truck, a diesel generator, a natural gas cogenerator, etc. regular maintenance will be needed (Appr. 2 hours per week [Volter Oy 2015]. Note, that the machine is generally supposed to operate non-stop). But since the machinery is relying on standard combustion engine technology, even excluding advanced methods like turbo fuel injection, maintenance staff does not need any special high level of technical skills. Car maintenance and wood gas cogenerator maintenance are on the same technical level.

V.2 Economic and political sustainability

The general trend of the global wood gas generator market may be found in [Global Trend 2015]. An overview of the (national and regional) market and technology development (as of 2013) in Germany can be found in Section 4.3 of [DBFZ Report 21].

V.2.1 Decoupling. The introduction of renewable energy can also lead to what experts [Iida GEC 2015] call decoupling of profit and fossil and nuclear energy consumption, accompanied by decoupling of energy consumption and quality of living. The first means that nations like Germany and Denmark who reduce fossil and nuclear energy consumption and substantially increase renewable energy consumption follow a new pattern of solid economic growth decoupled from increases of fossil and nuclear energy consumption. The second refers to the increase in comfort of living in a clean environment, including high indoor air quality and indoor comfort environment, only available in modern ultra low energy buildings, while at the same time residential and education related energy consumption is reduced to a small fraction of the current values [PH handbook].

Fig. 10. The blue staples show the renewable share for the EU as a whole. The numbers are percentages of renewable energy as a share of final energy consumption [K. Haara, WBA, 2017, and sources cited there].

V.2.2 Sweden. In Sweden, the total standing forest wood volume, and thus the amount of stored carbon, has doubled in Sweden's forests in the previous hundred years, thanks to reforestation and good forest management [K. Haara, WBA, 2017]. This leads to security and price stability of domestic wood fuel supply. With 36.6% of final energy use in 2016 bioenergy has become the leading energy source in Sweden today. This development was possible, because the government provided long term stable incentives with broad support across all political parties. Moreover, an effective carbon tax was introduced based on the polluter pays principle. Nevertheless, direct subsidies were

limited, trust was rather put in market forces. Since Sweden does not own domestic fossil energy sources, there was no strong lobby for it. In the opposite, Sweden has a strong forest industry, combined with a strong forest owner association and finally a well-developed district heating system [K. Haara, WBA, 2017]. By 2014 statistics and 2020 targets since 2004 (Fig. 10), the share of renewable sources in gross final consumption of energy grew significantly in all EU Member States. With more than half (52.6%) of energy from renewable sources in its gross final consumption of energy, Sweden had by far in 2014 the highest share, ahead of Latvia and Finland (both 38.7%).

V.2.3 Austria. Austria is a 50% forest country. It currently has a continuously increasing wood stock of 1.1 Mio m³. 75% of the annual increase are used under sustainable and multifunctional premises. This forest industry provides 300,000 jobs (10% of the national work force) in 172,000 companies. The annual production corresponds to 12 billion Euros, generating a foreign trade surplus of nearly 4 billion Euros. In 2015 Austria covered 33% of its energy with renewables. Among them bioenergy has with 58.6% by far the lion share [M. Nobauer 2017]. In Austria biomass district heating included in 2015 already 129 CHP plants with output of 318MWel, delivering annually 2 GWh electricity and 4.5 GWh of heat energy. This rapid development, was promoted by government grants for new plants and heating grids, and strong supportive forest and agricultural policy as part of regional development programs [H. Kopetz, 2017].

V.2.4 Strawberry cake economics. On 28th of July, I drove from Dunnottar Castle at the North Sea along A90 to Edzel Castle in north eastern Scotland. In need for a coffee, I saw a farm shop sign along the road, and had fresh strawberry tart with cappuccino (Fig. 11). Nearly two months later, researching Spanner Re²'s homepage for this paper, I stumbled across a video about Castleton Fruit Farm in north eastern Scotland starting with two wood gas cogenerator units, later expanding to three. Operator Viorel Panait reports: "Since we installed the biomass CHP, the annual cost for electricity was reduced considerably, and the heat demand was covered all year round." [Spanner Castleton 2017]. Holiday photos, and Google quickly confirmed: I had enjoyed that very farm's superb strawberry cake but missed their wood gas cogenerators. Two days later, the penny finally dropped. As all Europeans know, a Scot will never spend one pence more than absolutely necessary. A Scottish farmer adopting wood gas CHP as the most economic solution for his energy needs, has more weight than the expert judgement of countless financial analysts: *Wood gas CHP is most economic.*

Fig. 11. Strawberry tart and cappuccino at Castleton Farm Shop.

VI. Conclusion

This paper reports on wood gas cogeneration projects in southern Germany, Austria and Finland. It includes a brief description of the general principle of wood gas cogeneration, and information on market development. The technology is found to be technologically, economically and politically sustainable.

VII. References

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